

Table 2. Important characteristics of Bengawan Solo and Pandanwangi.

Character	Bengawan Solo	Pandanwangi
Yield (t/ha)	4.0-6.5	3.0-5.0
Plant height (cm)	100	150
Days to maturity	116	160
1,000-grain weight (g)	20	28
Head rice recovery (%)	80	80
Grain length (mm)	5.9	6.5
Grain length-breadth ratio	2.7	2.2
Anylose content (%)	17	23
Cooking quality	Soft	Tender
Aroma	Strong	Medium

Cianjur, West Java. The area of aromatic rice is expected to increase as cultivation of Bengawan Solo spreads in the major rice-producing areas in Indonesia. ■

Performance of experimental hybrids in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Eleven hybrids, MTU2000 through MTU2010, and two check varieties, Prabhat and Rasi, of different growth durations were evaluated for yield. The

experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications during 1992 kharif (monsoon) season. One seedling was planted per hill at 20- × 10- cm spacing. Plots were 9 m².

Data on quantitative traits (see table) were recorded. Standard heterosis (%) for yield over the checks was also estimated.

Most of the hybrids outyielded the check variety of similar duration. MTU2008 had the highest yield (5.9 t/ha)

with 38.3% standard heterosis over Prabhat followed by MTU2003 (5.8 t/ha) with 35.9% heterosis and MTU2002 (5.4 t/ha) with 26.3% heterosis. MTU2004 yielded 3.4 t/ha with 28.5% heterosis over Rasi.

These hybrids have performed well around Andhra Pradesh. The highest yielding hybrids had long slender grains. The checks had medium bold and short bold grains. ■

Performance of experimental hybrids at Rice Research Unit, Bapatla, Andhra Pradesh, India. 1992 kharif.

Hybrid/ check	Parentage	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Ear-bearing tillers/m ² (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000- grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Standard heterosis (%) at 5% over	
										Prabhat	Rasi
MTU2000	IR62829 A/MTU SN 26	114	86	330	24.5	71.5	20.3	5.2	MS	22.8*	95.9*
MTU2001	IR62829 A/MTU SN 27	111	92	298	25.4	64.5	21.3	5.2	MS	21.6*	72.7*
MTU2002	IR58025 A/MTU SN 26	115	86	306	24.1	55.3	20.5	5.4	MS	26.3*	101.5*
MTU2003	IR58025 A/MTU SN 27	116	95	300	24.6	67.8	21.1	5.8	LS	35.9*	116.8*
MTU2004	IR58025 A/MTU SN 4	97	75	258	22.0	59.2	22.3	3.4	LS	(-) 19.5*	28.5*
MTU2005	IR62829 A/MTU SN 3	94	74	262	25.5	76.9	19.3	3.1	MS	(-) 27.7*	15.3 ns
MTU2006	IR62829 A/MTU SN 4	100	71	297	22.2	67.4	21.4	3.4	LS	(-) 20.6*	26.6*
MTU2007	IR62829 A/MTU SN 15	89	63	271	18.3	41.7	20.9	2.6	MS	(-) 38.7*	(-) 2.2 ns
MTU2008	IR62829 A/MTU SN 22	111	82	317	23.4	84.4	22.5	5.9	LS	38.3*	120.6*
MTU2009	IR62829 A/MTU SN 36	105	85	287	26.6	71.8	21.2	4.8	MS	11.9 ns	78.6*
MTU2010	IR62829 A/MTU SN 40	93	71	323	19.4	40.2	21.0	2.4	MS	(-) 43.5*	(-) 9.7 ns
Prabhat	Check	111	78	253	20.2	86.9	27.1	4.3	MB		
Rasi	Check	90	75	231	20.1	81.7	20.0	2.7	SB		

GM 4.10
CD (0.05) 0.63
CV (%) 9.20

^aMS = medium slender, LS = long slender, MB = medium bold, SB = short bold. * = Heterosis is statistically significant at the 5% level using LSD test, ns = not significant.